

УДК 635.13:631.54:

PREPARATION OF PROSPEROUS CARROT VARIETIES IN REPUBLIC PERIOD IN ISLAND COASTAL AREAS*Rakhmatov Anvar Mamatovich, DSc., senior researcher**The head of the laboratory of the scientific research institute of vegetables, pulses and potatoes anvar.rakhmatov.85@mail.ru**Rejabov Mirjalal Choriyevich, intern researcher (PhD)**Scientific-research institute of vegetables, pulse crops and potatoes**Soliyev Ziyoiddin Shuhratbekovich is a junior researcher**Scientific Research Institute of Vegetables, Fruit Crops and Potatoes, Andijan Scientific Experimental Station***Abstract**

This article provides information on the preparation of mothers for the purpose of seed production of the Faravon variety of carrots included in the State Register in the island regions. In the experiments, morpho-biological and biometric measurements were carried out during technical ripening of the root fruit before digging. The length of the tubers of the Faravan variety was 13.1 cm, and the width was 4.2 cm. The average weight of one tuber was 112 g. A total yield of 28.9 t/ha per hectare was achieved. 85 percent of them were mothers of good quality. From the point of view of mother rootstock production, rootstocks that can be used as motherstocks have been produced.

Keywords: carrot, leaf shape, cultivation, development periods, productivity, root, and fruit weight.

Абстрактный

В данной статье приведены сведения о подготовке маточников с целью семеноводства сорта моркови Фаравон, включенного в Госреестр в островных регионах. В опытах проводили морфобиологические и биометрические измерения в период технического созревания корнеплодов перед выкопкой. Длина клубней сорта Фараван составила 13,1 см, а ширина 4,2 см. Средняя масса одного клубня составила 112 г. Достигнута общая урожайность 28,9 т/га с гектара. 85 процентов из них были матерями хорошего качества. С точки зрения производства маточных подвоев были получены подвои, которые можно использовать в качестве маточных подвоев.

Introduction. In recent years, the volume of production of vegetables, potatoes, and potatoes in our country has significantly exceeded the level of consumption, comprehensive

measures have been implemented to ensure the food security of the population, to fully satisfy the needs for vegetable products, and to expand their assortment. As a result, Uzbekistan became one of the world's leading countries in the production of vegetables and fruit products.

At present, carrots are grown in countries on the surface of the earth, and the cultivated area is 784 thousand hectares. Most of them are planted in Asian countries, the cultivated area is 364 thousand hectares or 46.4%. Carrot crops are root vegetables that are planted in open ground in early spring or in the planting half of summer in our republic, and the ninety-five method.

In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, i.e., in the insular regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, expanding the development of vegetable growing, applying varieties with a high level of profitability for cultivation, meeting the population's demand for this product and increasing the income of farmers through the establishment of seed production is being considered. During the visit of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Republic of Karakalpakstan on February 23-24, 2022, special assignments were given on the above topical issues.

Based on the above, we focused our scientific research on the preparation of mothers for seed production of the Faravon variety of carrots included in the State Register, and on the introduction of seed production in the island regions.

Main part: Description of the Faravan variety of carrots: A new variety that can be grown in different periods. The root fruit is red, weighs 100–120 g, is cylindrical, has a blunt tip, and the core is small. Productivity is 38-40 t/ha.

Figure 1. Prosperous variety

Based on the above, the second decade of July was chosen for the preparation of mother seeds from the Faravan carrot variety, and the seeds were planted in the ground. Carrot seeds were treated with seed (Kurt) drugs recommended by SPEvaKITI scientists and planted in SOM-

1 monoblock seeders (50+20)/2x10cm scheme, the results of phenological monitoring of crops are presented in Table 1 below.

The Faravon variety of carrots germinated in 19 days when the seeds were sown on July 20.

Table 1

Duration of the development phases of the "Faravon" carrot variety, 2021-2022.

Planting scheme	The day the seeds are sown	Germination of seedlings,		After germination, day				
		10%	75%	until the leaf appears	Until 5-6 leaves appear	formation of root and fruit	Motherhood until the seeds are formed	Harvest until collection
(50+20)/2x10cm	19-july	12	19	8	20	45	65	107

After the seeds fully germinated, it took 8 days for the first true leaf to appear, 20 days for the formation of 5-6 leaves, and 65 days for the technical ripening of the tubers. It took 107 days from germination to collection of mother seeds.

In the experiments, morpho-biological and biometric measurements were carried out in crops, Table 2. The Faravon variety of carrots grown in the Aralboyi region had 11.5 leaves, 33.5 cm in length, and 8.7 cm in width before digging.

Table 2

The effect of carrot variety Faravan on the number and size of leaves, 2021-2022

Sowing periods	At the end of the growing season			
	number of leaves, pcs	leaf width, cm	leaf length, cm	Index
July 20	11,5	8,7	33,5	3,85

Morpho-biological and biometric measurements were carried out before digging during technical ripening of the root.

The length of the tubers of the Faravan variety was 13.1 cm, and the width was 4.2 cm. The average weight of one tuber was 112 g.

The total yield per hectare was 28.9 t/ha. 85 percent of them were mothers of good quality. From the point of view of mother rootstock production, rootstocks that can be used as motherstocks have been produced.

Figure 2. In 2022, the Faravan variety of carrots will ripen technically

Single selections. To obtain original seeds from the Faravan variety, a selection of 100 percent plants was planted.

Each of the individual selection samples was evaluated according to the appearance of the fruit, fruit weight, and color of the fruit flesh.

Maternal seeds of carrots selected as a result of a single selection were used to maintain the purity of the variety, for subsequent planting and selection, and for large-scale propagation.

Special trenches are prepared for storing the prepared mothers. It was put into storage in these trenches at the end of November and kept until April 15.

Conclusion

1. Judging from the conducted research, it has been shown that it is desirable to grow Farovon carrots in the coastal regions of the island.
2. The "Farovon" carrot variety, when planted on July 20, takes 107 days from germination to collection of mother seeds.

3. The "Farovon" variety of carrots made 28.9 t/ha. 85 percent of them were mothers of good quality. From the point of view of mother rootstock production, rootstocks that can be used as motherstocks have been produced.

Used literature

1. Руководство по управлению засоленными почвами. Продовольственная и сельскохозяйственная организация Объединенных Наций. ФАО, Рим. 2017. С. 5-27.
2. Raxmatov A.M. The Effect of Mineral Fertilizers on the Yield of a Leaf Turnip Plant. Published on the journal of «Middle European Scientific Bulletin» Volume - 28 (2022) September ISSN (E): 2694-9970. Impact Factor: 5.985. Page No 46-49.
3. Raxmatov A.M. Effect of Irrigation Procedure on Productivity of Turnips for Salad. Journal of Innovative Studies of Engineering Science (JISES) Volume: 01 Issue: 03 2022 ISSN: 2751-7578 <http://innosci.org/> . Impact Factor: 9.1. Page No 67-69.
4. Raxmatov A.M. Influence of planting period on the biochemical composition of leaf turnip. Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress (JARSP). Vol. 2 No. 2 (2023): Page No 10-12. (Impact Factor: 8.1).
5. Raxmatov A.M. Creation of flower varieties in the process of selection. International journal of biological engineering and agriculture: Vol. 2 No. 2 (2023): Page No 7-9. (Impact Factor: 8.1).